

Protocol for human peripheral nerve processing

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If protocol is used, please cite as follows:

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DAY OF SURGERY:

Prepare

- Tubes with 4% PFA for histology
 - Immediately immerse tissue in 4% paraformaldehyde (overnight at room temperature), make sure nerve is straight and mark distal/proximal if required
- Tube with RNA later for gene expression
 - immediately immerse tissue in RNAlater (5-10x volume of nerve sample)
 - incubate overnight at 4 degrees (~16 hours)
- Tube with MACS buffer for cell isolation
 - Immediately immerse tissue in MACS buffer which is at all times kept at 4 degrees and sample always fully immersed.
 - Soon after surgery, the tissue is weighed and washed once with 10 ml of HBSS/20 mM HEPES
 - Then, the tissue is transferred to 1 ml CryoStor CS10
 - Keep the tube on ice for 10 minutes
 - Insert the tube within the CoolCell[®] and place the CoolCell[®] into -80°C freezer allowing the temperature to slowly reduce
 - The next day, transfer the cryo-preserved tissue to a liquid nitrogen tank for long-term storage

The pieces are optimally at least 0.5cm long.

1-3 DAY AFTER SURGERY

Histological analysis (PFA):

- the day after surgery, wash tissue in 0.1M phosphate buffer
- Immerse in 20% sucrose in 0.1M PB. Keep at 4 degrees for 3 days.
- On 3rd day, freeze the nerve in OCT, marking distal/proximal if required and store at -80 degrees

RNA analysis (RNAlater):

- The day after surgery: working in a RNase free environment, cut away connective tissue and store the nerve in new RNase free tube
- Store the tube (pierced) at -80 degrees